

Effects of an Eight-Week Basic Swimming Training Program on Kinanthropometric Characteristics, Flexibility, and Muscular Strength in Girls and Boys Aged 6–13 Years

8 Haftalık Temel Yüzme Eğitiminin 6–13 Yaş Kız ve Erkek Çocuklarda Kinantropometrik Özellikler, Esneklik ve Kas Kuvveti Üzerine Etkileri

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the effects of an eight-week basic swimming training program on kinanthropometric characteristics, flexibility, and muscular strength among girls and boys attending swimming courses. A total of 37 volunteer children aged 6–13 years, including 22 girls and 15 boys, participated in the study. A quantitative research method with a single-group pretest–posttest experimental design was employed. At the beginning and end of the training program, height, body weight, arm span, hand length, and foot length were measured. Flexibility was assessed using the Sit-and-Reach Test, while muscular strength was evaluated using a handgrip dynamometer. Descriptive statistics were calculated, and a paired-samples t-test was used to determine differences between pretest and posttest measurements.

The findings showed statistically significant increases in height, body weight, arm span, hand length, and foot length from pretest to posttest ($p < 0.05$). However, no statistically significant differences were found in body mass index (BMI), flexibility, or handgrip strength ($p > 0.05$). In conclusion, the eight-week basic swimming training program appears to be associated with positive changes in certain kinanthropometric characteristics among children aged 6–13 years.

Keywords: Swimming, kinanthropometric characteristics, muscular strength, flexibility.

Öz

Bu çalışmanın amacı, yüzme kurslarına katılan kız ve erkek çocuklara uygulanan sekiz haftalık temel yüzme eğitiminin kinantropometrik özellikler, esneklik ve kas kuvveti üzerindeki etkilerini incelemektir. Araştırmaya 6–13 yaş aralığında toplam 37 gönüllü çocuk, 22 kız ve 15 erkek, katılmıştır. Çalışmada nicel araştırma yöntemi kapsamında tek gruplu ön test–son test deneysel desen kullanılmıştır. Eğitim programının başlangıcında ve sonunda katılımcıların boy, vücut ağırlığı, kulaç uzunluğu, el uzunluğu ve ayak uzunluğu ölçümleri alınmıştır. Esneklik düzeyi Otur-Eriş Testi ile, kas kuvveti ise el kavrama kuvveti dinamometresi ile değerlendirilmiştir. Verilerin analizinde tanımlayıcı istatistikler hesaplanmış ve ön test ile son test ölçümleri arasındaki farkın belirlenmesi amacıyla bağımlı örneklem t-testi kullanılmıştır.

Araştırma bulgularına göre, ön testten son teste katılımcıların boy, vücut ağırlığı, kulaç uzunluğu, el uzunluğu ve ayak uzunluğu değerlerinde istatistiksel olarak anlamlı artışlar belirlenmiştir ($p < 0.05$). Buna karşın beden kitle indeksi (BKİ), esneklik ve el kavrama kuvveti değişkenlerinde anlamlı bir farklılık tespit edilmemiştir ($p > 0.05$). Sonuç olarak, sekiz haftalık temel yüzme eğitiminin 6–13 yaş grubundaki çocukların bazı kinantropometrik özelliklerinde olumlu değişimlerle ilişkili olduğu söylenebilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yüzme, kinantropometrik özellikler, kas kuvveti, esneklik.

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Introduction

Movement is one of the fundamental characteristics of human life and is regarded as an important indicator of vitality, health, and functional capacity (Kolukısa & Dizdar, 2022). However, in the 21st century, technological advancements have significantly influenced daily routines, transportation, and work environments, leading to a decline in individuals' physical activity levels and the widespread adoption of sedentary lifestyles (Coşkuntürk et al., 2023; Yılmaz, 2014). Prolonged inactivity, excessive screen exposure, and passive lifestyle habits have been associated with numerous adverse outcomes, including obesity, musculoskeletal disorders, fatigue, social isolation, and behavioural problems (Ceyhan & Çakır, 2021; Yel et al., 2024). Therefore, physical activity and sport are considered essential not only for performance enhancement but also for maintaining a healthy lifestyle, promoting social adaptation, and improving overall quality of life.

Sport is a multidimensional phenomenon that supports individuals' physical, cognitive, emotional, and social development. Regular exercise contributes significantly to health maintenance, rehabilitation, performance improvement, and the mitigation of the negative effects of physical inactivity (Mühürhancı Dal, 2011; Çolakoğlu & Şenel, 2003). Indeed, even low-intensity physical activities have been reported to improve the health status of sedentary individuals (Biçer et al., 2009; Gönen et al., 2022). Participation in physical activity during childhood is particularly critical for supporting growth and developmental processes. Through games, physical education, and sporting activities, children develop motor skills while simultaneously strengthening social relationships, self-confidence, and psychological well-being (Coşkuntürk et al., 2023; Kaplan & Gülten, 2017).

In recent years, reduced access to safe play areas, increased reliance on technology, and the growing prevalence of screen-based lifestyles have contributed to lower physical activity among children. This trend may negatively affect developmental parameters, including muscular strength, flexibility, coordination, and fundamental motor skills. Considering that movement habits acquired during childhood are closely associated with health outcomes later in life, directing children toward appropriate sports disciplines at an early age has become increasingly important (Özgül et al., 2015; Muratlı, 2013). In this context, swimming emerges as one of the most prominent sports that effectively supports children's physical and motor development.

Swimming is a sport in which the entire body musculature is actively engaged, water's buoyancy reduces joint loading, the risk of injury is relatively low, and participation can be sustained throughout the lifespan (Selçuk, 2013; Yapıcı et al., 2016). During swimming, multiple biomotor components—including coordination, strength, flexibility, endurance, balance, and rhythm—are simultaneously utilised and developed (Yfanti et al., 2014; Sammoud et al., 2018). Furthermore, swimming has been shown to enhance cardiovascular and respiratory function, support musculoskeletal health, promote postural development, and enhance psychological well-being (Nualnim et al., 2012; Saavedra et al., 2007; Cox et al., 2010; Kargarfard et al., 2012).

Anthropometric characteristics, muscular strength, flexibility, and coordination are among the key determinants of swimming performance and the acquisition of fundamental swimming skills. Sammoud et al. (2018) categorised factors influencing swimming performance into physical fitness level, technical skills, psychological attributes, and anthropometric structure. In particular, flexibility in the shoulders, trunk, hips, and ankles plays a critical role in the proper execution of swimming techniques, while muscular strength is considered a fundamental factor in overcoming water resistance and increasing swimming speed (Rushall, 2009; Sanders et al., 2011; Barbosa et al., 2010; Toussaint & Beek, 1992). Therefore, examining the effects of basic swimming training in children is important not only for skill acquisition but also for physical development and motor competence.

Previous studies have demonstrated that swimming training improves children's physical, physiological, motor, and anthropometric characteristics. Çelebi (2008) reported that regular swimming

training improves children's physiological and motor abilities, while Yiğit (2011) indicated that swimming training supports anthropometric development. Selçuk (2013) reported significant improvements in performance indicators, including sit-ups, push-ups, handgrip strength, speed, and flexibility, following swimming training. Similarly, Yılmaz (2014) and Özerdinç (2017) reported that swimming training has a positive impact on biomotor, physical, physiological, and strength-related parameters. Nevertheless, studies examining the combined effects of basic swimming training on flexibility, muscular strength, and anthropometric parameters associated with motor development—particularly among boys and girls aged 6–13 years—remain limited.

Although the existing literature includes studies investigating the effects of swimming training on children's physical development parameters, research addressing the combined influence of short-term basic swimming programs on kinanthropometric characteristics, flexibility, and muscular strength remains scarce. Accordingly, the present study is expected to contribute to the literature by examining the effects of a short-term basic swimming training program on various indicators of physical development through a comprehensive and integrative approach.

In this context, the primary aim of the present study is to investigate the effects of an eight-week basic swimming training program applied to boys and girls aged 6–13 years on flexibility, muscular strength, and anthropometric parameters associated with motor development. It is anticipated that the findings of this study will reveal the developmental contributions of basic swimming training in children and provide valuable insights for planning swimming education programs and advancing the sports science literature.

METHOD

Research Design

In the present study, a quantitative research approach employing a single-group pretest–posttest experimental design was utilised to examine the effects of basic swimming training on kinanthropometric characteristics, flexibility, and muscular strength. Experimental designs allow researchers to examine changes in dependent variables before and after the implementation of an independent variable (Ekiz, 2003).

The single-group pretest–posttest model involves collecting data from the same group of participants before and after an intervention (Gay & Airasian, 2000; Karasar, 2012). In this study, the aforementioned experimental design was preferred due to the practical difficulties associated with establishing a demographically comparable control group.

Study Group

The study population consisted of individuals participating in swimming courses held at the semi-Olympic swimming pool affiliated with the Provincial Directorate of Youth and Sports in Bayburt, Türkiye. The study sample comprised 37 children aged 6 to 13 years who attended swimming courses at the Bayburt Semi-Olympic Swimming Pool between February and June 2025.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Gender	N	%
Female	22	59.5
Male	15	40.5
Total	37	100
Age (years)	N	%
6	5	13.5
7	2	5.4
8	10	27
9	4	10.8
10	7	18.9
11	3	8.1
12	5	13.5
13	1	2.7
Total	37	100

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the participants. A total of 37 children participated in the study, of whom 22 were female (59.5%) and 15 were male (40.5%). The participants' ages ranged from 6 to 13 years, with the highest proportion observed in the 8-year-old age group (27.0%) and the lowest in the 13-year-old age group (2.7%).

To determine the study group, the convenience sampling method, a purposive sampling technique, was employed. Convenience sampling is a nonprobability sampling method that collects data from individuals who are readily accessible and willing to participate in the study (Malhotra, 2004; Haşiloğlu et al., 2015).

Data Collection Instruments

In the present study, standardised measurement instruments were used to determine the anthropometric and physical fitness characteristics of the participants. Body weight was measured using a digital scale; height was measured with a wall-mounted stadiometer; arm span was measured using a measuring tape; hand length was measured with a ruler; and foot length was measured using a portable foot length measuring device.

Flexibility was assessed using the Sit-and-Reach test, while muscular strength was evaluated using a TKK 5401 digital hand dynamometer.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection process in this study was systematically planned and implemented. Prior to data collection, ethical approval was obtained from the Bayburt University Ethics Committee, with decision number 44 dated 12 December 2024, and the necessary permissions were secured from the relevant institutions. All participants and their parents or legal guardians were informed of the study's purpose and procedures, and written informed consent was obtained on a voluntary basis.

Pretest measurements were conducted before the commencement of the swimming training program. Participants' height, body weight, arm span, hand length, foot length, flexibility, and handgrip strength were measured according to standardised procedures. To enhance the reliability of the measurements, body weight was measured three times, while flexibility and handgrip strength were measured twice, and the average values were recorded.

Following completion of the pretest measurements, participants attended an eight-week basic swimming training program. The training program consisted of 16 sessions.

Upon completion of the training program, posttest measurements were conducted using the same instruments and procedures as in the pretest phase. The collected data were subsequently analysed and reported.

Ethics Statement

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Bayburt University Ethics Committee with decision number 44 dated 12 December 2024. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants prior to participation.

Data Analysis

The data obtained from the study were analysed using appropriate statistical methods. Prior to the analysis, the data distribution was examined to determine the suitability of parametric statistical tests.

Table 2. Normality Test of Data Distribution

Variables	n	Skewness	Std. Error	Kurtosis	Std. Error
Height Pretest	37	-.434	.388	-.694	.759
Weight Pretest	37	.001	.388	-.635	.759
BMI Pretest	37	.503	.388	-.357	.759
Arm Span Pretest	37	-.452	.388	-.459	.759
Left Hand Length Pretest	37	-.749	.388	.113	.759
Right Hand Length Pretest	37	-.762	.388	.194	.759
Left Foot Length Pretest	37	-.529	.388	-.125	.759
Right Foot Length Pretest	37	-.591	.388	-.111	.759
Sit-and-Reach Pretest	37	-.002	.388	-.389	.759
Left Handgrip Strength Pretest	37	.012	.388	-.672	.759
Right Handgrip Strength Pretest	37	.695	.388	-.265	.759
Height Posttest	37	-.439	.388	-.701	.759
Weight Posttest	37	.050	.388	-.609	.759
BMI Posttest	37	.521	.388	-.383	.759
Arm Span Posttest	37	-.460	.388	-.489	.759
Left Hand Length Posttest	37	-.685	.388	.326	.759
Right Hand Length Posttest	37	-.736	.388	.316	.759
Left Foot Length Posttest	37	-.492	.388	-.455	.759
Right Foot Length Posttest	37	-.534	.388	-.321	.759
Sit-and-Reach Posttest	37	-.077	.388	-.792	.759
Left Handgrip Strength Posttest	37	-.153	.388	-1.149	.759
Right Handgrip Strength Posttest	37	.333	.388	-.941	.759

The skewness and kurtosis coefficients were examined to determine whether the pretest and posttest data for the variables showed normal distributions. It was observed that the skewness and kurtosis values for all variables fell within the range of -2 to $+2$. This range is widely accepted as a sufficient criterion for assuming normality of the data (George & Mallery, 2010).

Accordingly, the data obtained in the present study were considered normally distributed, indicating that the assumptions for parametric statistical tests were met.

Descriptive statistics, including arithmetic mean and standard deviation values, were calculated for all variables. To determine differences between pretest and posttest measurements, a paired-samples t-test was employed. In addition, Cohen's d effect size was calculated for all variables in order to assess the magnitude of the observed changes.

Table 3. General Content of the Eight-Week Basic Swimming Training Program

Week	Number of Sessions	Content
Week 1	2 sessions	Warm-up exercises, introduction to pool rules, basic kicking exercises, breathing exercises
Week 2	2 sessions	Coordination of kicking and breathing, forward movement in water using a kickboard
Week 3	2 sessions	Kicking exercises with a kickboard and preparatory arm stroke drills
Week 4	2 sessions	Instruction of right and left arm stroke techniques, continuation of kicking practice
Week 5	2 sessions	Side breathing techniques, coordination of arm strokes and breathing

Week 6	2 sessions	Streamline position without a kickboard, coordination of arm strokes and breathing
Week 7	2 sessions	Continuous swimming practice, coordination of stroke–breathing–kicking movements
Week 8	2 sessions	Freestyle swimming practice and technical corrections

Participants were enrolled in a basic swimming training program consisting of 16 sessions over 8 weeks, held twice per week. Each session commenced with approximately 15 minutes of warm-up exercises, followed by structured activities focusing on kicking techniques, breathing control, arm stroke mechanics, and overall swimming coordination.

RESULTS

The findings related to the pretest and posttest comparisons of anthropometric characteristics, flexibility, and handgrip strength are presented in Tables 4–14. Statistically significant increases were observed in height, body weight, arm span, hand length, and foot length, whereas no significant differences were found in BMI, flexibility, or handgrip strength.

Table 4. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Height Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Height (cm)	Pretest	134.4946	37	11.98777	1.97078	-13.598	.001	-2.236
	Posttest	135.3054	37	12.01880	1.97588			

When Table 4 is examined, a statistically significant difference is observed between the participants' pretest and posttest mean height measurements ($t = -13.598$, $p < .05$). The mean height value in the posttest ($\bar{x} = 135.3054$) was found to be higher than that recorded in the pretest ($\bar{x} = 134.4946$).

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d value was -2.236 , and its absolute magnitude indicated a large effect size, according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 5. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Body Weight Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Body Weight (kg)	Pretest	35.8722	37	10.90564	1.79288	-3.899	.001	-.641
	Posttest	36.2762	37	10.99934	1.80828			

When Table 5 is examined, a statistically significant difference is observed between the participants' pretest and posttest mean body weight values ($t = -3.899$, $p < .05$). The mean body weight in the posttest ($\bar{x} = 36.2762$) was found to be higher than that recorded in the pretest ($\bar{x} = 35.8722$).

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d effect size was -0.641 , indicating a moderate effect size according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 6. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Body Mass Index (BMI) Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Body Mass Index (BMI) (kg/m ²)	Pretest	19.3054	37	3.84967	.63288	-1.188	.852	-.031
	Posttest	19.3162	37	3.84950	.63285			

When Table 6 is examined, no statistically significant difference was found between the participants' pretest and posttest mean BMI values ($t = -1.188$, $p > .05$). The posttest mean BMI ($\bar{x} = 19.3162$) did not differ significantly from the pretest mean ($\bar{x} = 19.3054$).

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d effect size was -0.031, indicating a very small (negligible) effect size according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 7. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Arm Span Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Arm Span (cm)	Pretest	128.4973	37	10.38906	1.70795	-14.283	.001	-2.348
	Posttest	129.5568	37	10.41016	1.71142			

When Table 7 is examined, a statistically significant difference was found between participants' pretest and posttest mean arm span values ($t = -14.283$, $p < .05$). Posttest values were higher than pretest values, indicating improvement following the intervention.

The calculated Cohen's d value was -2.348, and its absolute magnitude indicated a large effect size.

Table 8. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Left Hand Length Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Left Hand Length (cm)	Pretest	14.8811	37	1.36582	.22454	-8.105	.001	-1.332
	Posttest	15.1189	37	1.36399	.22424			

When Table 8 is examined, a statistically significant difference was observed between the participants' pretest and posttest mean left hand length values ($t = -8.105$, $p < .05$). The mean left hand length in the posttest ($\bar{x} = 15.1189$) was found to be higher than that recorded in the pretest ($\bar{x} = 14.8811$).

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d effect size was -1.332, indicating a large effect size according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 9. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Right Hand Length Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Right Hand Length (cm)	Pretest	14,8946	37	1,36421	,22428	-8,437	.001	-1,387
	Posttest	15,1405	37	1,38433	,22758			

When Table 9 is examined, a statistically significant difference was observed between the participants' pretest and posttest mean right-hand length values ($t = -8.437$, $p < .05$). The mean right-hand length in the posttest ($\bar{x} = 15.1405$) was found to be higher than that recorded in the pretest ($\bar{x} = 14.8946$).

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d effect size was -1.387, indicating a large effect size according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 10. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Left Foot Length Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Left Foot Length (cm)	Pretest	21.0162	37	1.81254	.29798	-8.823	.001	-1.450
	Posttest	21.3676	37	1.81109	.29774			

According to Table 10, a statistically significant difference was found between the participants' pretest and posttest mean left foot length values ($t = -8.823$, $p < .05$). The posttest values were higher than the pretest values, indicating an improvement following the intervention.

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d effect size was -1.450, indicating a large effect size according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 11. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Right Foot Length Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Right Foot Length (cm)	Pretest	21.0324	37	1.81813	.29890	-9.769	.001	-1.606
	Posttest	21.3568	37	1.77882	.29244			

According to Table 11, a statistically significant difference was found between participants' pretest and posttest mean right-foot length values ($t = -9.769$, $p < .05$). Posttest values were higher than pretest values, indicating improvement following the intervention.

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d effect size was -1.606 , indicating a large effect size according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 12. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Flexibility Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Flexibility (cm)	Pretest	26.6068	37	5.57346	.91627	.227	.822	.037
	Posttest	26.4662	37	6.48562	1.06623			

When Table 12 is examined, no statistically significant difference was found between the participants' pretest and posttest mean flexibility values ($t = 0.227$, $p > .05$).

Furthermore, the calculated Cohen's d effect size was 0.037 , indicating a very small (negligible) effect size according to conventional interpretation criteria.

Table 13. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Left Handgrip Strength Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Left Handgrip Strength (kg)	Pretest	13.7027	37	4.89877	.80535	-.141	.889	-.023
	Posttest	13.7622	37	4.67783	.76903			

According to Table 13, no statistically significant difference was found between the participants' pretest and posttest mean left handgrip strength values ($t = -0.141$, $p > .05$). The calculated effect size was very small (negligible) ($d = -0.023$).

Table 14. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Right Handgrip Strength Measurements

Variable		Mean	n	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p	d
Right Handgrip Strength (kg)	Pretest	14.3581	37	5.69664	.93652	.052	.959	.009
	Posttest	14.3351	37	5.82015	.95683			

According to Table 14, no statistically significant difference was found between the participants' pretest and posttest mean right handgrip strength values ($t = 0.052$, $p > .05$). The calculated effect size was very small (negligible) ($d = 0.009$).

Discussion, Conclusion, and Recommendations

In the present study, the effects of basic swimming training conducted in swimming pools on kinanthropometric characteristics, flexibility, and muscular strength were examined, and the findings were evaluated in light of the participants' age range and gender distribution. The results of the study

indicate that the effects of swimming training on physical development are shaped by factors such as age, gender, training duration, program content, and individual developmental stage. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that these parameters should be systematically considered to achieve the desired outcomes. In this context, the discussion and conclusions regarding the research findings are presented below within a comprehensive, integrative framework.

Swimming is one of the important sports disciplines that contributes to individuals' physical, social, and emotional development. It is among the activities in which individuals of all ages participate for sport or recreational purposes through courses organised by various public institutions or private organisations. From this perspective, swimming is regarded as one of the fundamental physical activities that support physical development during childhood.

In the present study, which aimed to evaluate the effects of basic swimming training conducted in swimming pools on various participant-related variables, it was determined that basic swimming training was associated with a positive, statistically significant increase in participants' height. Similarly, a significant increase in participants' mean body weight was observed. When these results are considered collectively, it can be suggested that an eight-week structured basic swimming training program may contribute positively to the anthropometric development of individuals aged 6–13 years.

However, since height and body weight are directly associated with natural growth and developmental processes, it is more appropriate to interpret the observed increases not solely as the effect of swimming training, but also in conjunction with developmental processes. Yörükoğlu and Koz (2007) emphasised that developmental factors substantially influence physical growth during childhood.

The literature indicates that numerous studies support the effect of swimming training on height development. In a study by Dilek (2004) on swimmers, participants' mean height increased. Similarly, in a study by Güler (2000), it was found that height increased among individuals in the same age group. International studies have also suggested that swimming training may support children's height development (Allen et al., 1997; Novak et al., 1973). In this context, the findings of the present study are generally consistent with the existing literature.

Within the scope of the study, no statistically significant difference was detected between the pretest and posttest measurements of Body Mass Index (BMI) values. However, a slight increase in participants' mean BMI was observed. This finding suggests that short-term swimming training may have a limited effect on BMI. Similarly, Tsalis et al. (2004) reported that a training program implemented with adolescent swimmers aged 12–17 years did not result in a statistically significant change in BMI values. This situation may be explained by the fact that BMI is influenced not only by physical activity but also by multiple factors, including nutritional habits, metabolic processes, and physiological characteristics associated with growth and development during adolescence.

According to the present study's findings, basic swimming training also produced positive effects on individuals' anthropometric measurements. In this regard, statistically significant increases in participants' arm span measurements were observed from pretest to posttest. Arm span is an important parameter for swimming performance, influencing distance covered and movement efficiency. These results indicate that anthropometric length measurements increased over the eight-week training period.

When studies in the literature are examined, it is observed that findings differ regarding the effects of swimming training on arm span. In a study by Anderson et al. (2008) of elite swimmers followed over a long period, a significant increase in arm span was observed. Similarly, in research by Damsgaard et al. (2001), improvements in children's body proportions were observed. In contrast, Polat et al. (2003) found no significant difference in arm span among children aged 14 years. These differences may be associated with variations in the age characteristics of the study groups and their developmental stages.

Among the other anthropometric measurements examined in the study were hand and foot length. The findings revealed that individuals aged 6–13 years who participated in basic swimming training

demonstrated positive development in right- and left-hand length and foot length. Given the influence of physical development on sports performance, these results suggest that physical performance indicators increased alongside the basic swimming training process.

These findings are consistent with those reported in a study by Atasoy (2018) with performance-group swimmers aged 8–10 years. In that study, a significant difference was found between pretest and posttest hand length measurements. In contrast, Işıldak (2013) did not observe a significant difference in anthropometric length measurements in a study conducted with swimmers aged 12–15 years. The emergence of these differences may be attributed to the age characteristics and developmental stages of the research groups, which can be considered determining factors.

Findings related to the development of foot length also show similarities with certain studies reported in the literature. In a study by Anderson et al. (2008) of elite swimmers, a significant increase in foot length was observed. Conversely, in another study carried out by Atasoy (2018), no significant difference was observed in foot length measurements. This situation indicates that factors such as the characteristics of the study group, training level, and program structure may play a determining role in anthropometric development.

According to the study's results, no statistically significant difference was observed between the pretest and posttest measurements for the flexibility parameter. This finding suggests that the eight-week basic swimming training program may not have provided a sufficient duration for the development of flexibility. Similarly, in a study conducted by Zülkadiroğlu (1995), no significant difference was observed in flexibility measurements. International research has also indicated that swimming training may have a limited effect on flexibility (Dawson et al., 2002). This situation indicates that flexibility development is a physical characteristic that requires continuity and regular training.

In the handgrip strength test applied in the study to determine strength development, no statistically significant difference was found between the pretest and posttest measurements. This result may be attributed to the limited inclusion of exercises directly targeting strength development within the basic swimming training program. In contrast, studies by Bayır (2023) and Karakuş et al. (2018) reported that swimming training improved strength development. It is considered that the primary reason for these differences may be variations in the content and duration of the training programs.

In general terms, the findings of the present study indicate that swimming training may be associated with children's physical development parameters. While positive developments were observed in height and anthropometric measurements, it was recognised that the development of certain physical characteristics, such as flexibility and strength, requires longer-term, more systematic training programs. These findings reveal that the effects of swimming training on physical development are closely related to variables such as age, gender, training duration, program content, and individual developmental stages.

These results highlight the importance of organising the duration and content of basic swimming training programs in accordance with children's developmental stages when planning swimming education programs for young individuals.

Limitations

The present study has several limitations. First, the study used a single-group pretest–posttest design, and the absence of a control group may limit the generalizability of the findings. In addition, the relatively small sample size and the inclusion of participants across a broad age range may influence the interpretation of the results. Furthermore, the duration of the swimming training program, limited to eight weeks, may have prevented full observation of the development of certain physical characteristics, particularly flexibility and strength. The study is limited to data from 37 participants aged 6–13 years

who attended basic swimming training at a swimming pool operated by the Ministry of Youth and Sports in the city centre of Bayburt between February and June 2025.

Recommendations

For future studies, it is recommended that experimental designs incorporating control groups be employed. In this way, the effects of basic swimming training on children's physical development parameters can be evaluated more robustly. Additionally, conducting studies with larger sample groups and examining different age categories separately may enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Considering that no significant differences were observed in flexibility and handgrip strength variables following the eight-week basic swimming training program, it is recommended that future research implement longer-term programs supported by exercises specifically targeting strength and flexibility development. Moreover, planning basic swimming training programs in accordance with children's developmental stages may contribute to more effective monitoring of physical and motor development outcomes.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Author Contributions

K.G.K. contributed to data collection, data organization, and manuscript drafting. Z.Ç. contributed to study conception, supervision, methodology, academic guidance, interpretation of findings, and critical revision of the manuscript. Both authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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